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Bilgi ve Haberleşme Teknoloji Harcamaları ile İnovasyon İndeksinin Dünya Ülkeleri Arasındaki Yeri ve Korelasyon Analizi

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BİLGİ VE HABERLEŞME TEKNOLOJİ HARCAMALARI İLE İNOVASYON İNDEKSİNİN DÜNYA ÜLKELERİ ARASINDAKİ YERİ VE KORELASYON ANALİZİ

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ÖZET

Bu çalışmada; seçilmiş Dünya ülkelerinin, Küresel Özet İnovasyon İndeksi (Global Summary Innovation Index-GSII), GDP oranı içindeki bilgi ve haberleşme teknoloji harcamaları (GDP %) ve kişi başına düşen bilgi ve haberleşme teknoloji harcamaları göstergeleri kullanılarak, ülkelerin benzerlik ve farklılıklarının incelenmesi amaçlanmaktadır. Dünya Bankası göstergeleri kullanılmıştır. Bu amaçla Dünya Bankasından alınan değişkenlere; hiyerarşik kümeleme analizi, diskriminant analizi ve korelasyon analizi uygulanmıştır. Sonuç olarak; ilk grup ülkeleri Bulgaristan, İspanya, Yunanistan, İtalya, Meksika, Polonya, Portekiz, Romanya ve Rusya; ikinci grup ülkeleri İsviçre, Finlandiya, İngiltere, Japonya, Singapur, İsveç ve Amerika Birleşik Devletleri; üçüncü grup ülkeleri Avustralya, Avusturya, Belçika, Kanada, Almanya, Danimarka, Fransa, İrlanda, Hollanda ve Norveç; dördüncü grup ülkeleri Çin, Macaristan, Hindistan ve Slovak Cumhuriyeti.; beşinci grup ülkeleri İsrail ve Kore; altıncı grup ülkeleri Hong Kong ve Yeni Zelanda; yedinci grup ülkeleri Arjantin, Brezilya, Çek Cumhuriyeti, Türkiye ve Güney Afrika olarak görülmüştür. GSII ve kişi başına düşen bilgi ve haberleşme teknoloji harcamaları arasında 0.8702085 gibi yüksek denebilecek bir korelasyon, GSII ve GDP yüzdesi arasındaki korelasyon 0.4144508, GDP ve kişi başına düşen bilgi ve haberleşme teknoloji harcamaları arasındaki korelasyon 0.4296516 olarak bulunmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İnovasyon, Teknoloji, Gelişim, Harcama, Hiyerarşik Kümeleme, Diskriminant Analizi, Korelasyon Analizi.

ANALYSIS OF CORRELATION BETWEEN TECHNOLOGY EXPENDITURES AND INNOVATION CAPABILITIES OF WORLD COUNTRIES

ABSTRACT

In this study, it is aimed to compare of indicators Global Summary Innovation Index (GSII), information and communications technology expenditures of World countries. It is used World Bank indicators and applied the Hierarchical Clustering Method, Discriminant Analysis and Correlation Analysis. As a result, it is seemed first group countries; Bulgaria, Spain, Greece, Italy, Mexico, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Russia, second group countries; Switzerland, Finland, United Kingdom, Japan, Singapore, Sweden and USA, third group countries; Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Germany, Denmark, France, Ireland, Netherland and Norway, fourth group countries; China, Hungary, India and Slovak Republic, fifth group countries; Israel and Korea, sixth group countries; Hong Kong and New Zealand; seventh group countries; Argentina, Brazil, Czech Republic, Turkey and South Africa. It is found that high correlation between GSII and per capita of technologic expenditures is 0.8702085, correlation between GSII and % of GDP is 0.4144508, correlation of GDP and per capita of technologic expenditures is 0.4296516.

Key Words: Technology, Innovation, Expenditures, Hierarchical Clustering, Discriminant Analysis, Correlation Analysis.

1. Introduction

This article compares with “Global Summary Innovation Scoreboard” (GSII) with information and communications technology expenditures (% of GDP, per capita) some of World countries compares. Global innovation performance is measured by a composite index, the *Global Summary Innovation Index* (GSII). This composite index is calculated as follows for the both the base year and the reference year, i.e. the year for which most recent countries data are available (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Netherland, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovak Republic, Sweden, Switzerland, Norway, Turkey, Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, Hong Kong, India, Israel, Japan, New Zealand, Republic of Korea, Mexico, Russian Federation, Singapore, South Africa and the US.

In this article, Hierarchical and non hierarchic are used form the clustering methodology. Hierarchical analysis and to decide the number of the cluster, the hierarchical clustering method and decided as K -means form the n on hierarchical clustering method are compared. According to the K -means analysis, indicators are effective importantly among the selected indicators of $N = 39$ countries ($p < 0.05$). The discriminant analysis is used for testing the results of the clustering analysis and the high mean value, low Wilk’s Lambda and high cononic corellation values are provided.

Clustering analysis is used for separating units to homogeneous groups utilized calculating some measures based on similarity or dissimilarity between variables and describing certain prototypes. While clustering methods separate suitable groups or variables which are homogeneous within themselves and heterogeneous between themselves benefiting from distance or resemblance matrix, they are part with two elementary groups to determine groups (clustering) in respect of followed approach. They are hierarchical and nonhierarchical clustering methods (3).

Nonhierarchical Clustering Analysis is a method that aims at dividing clusters which are homogeneous within themselves and heterogeneous between themselves and that purposes estimating of sub-populations’ parameters (groups or cluster mean vectors and covariance matrixs) by the agency of prototype clusters. Meanwhile both of units and variables form clusters in various similarity levels with eachother in hierarchical clustering, it is aimed at grouping units to suitable clusters and splitting n units to k clusters. Nonhierarchical Clustering methods are K –Means and Medoid Clustering.

K -Means Clustering Method that minimizes square totals within clusters of continuous p variables which are obtained by a great number of units (N), aims to separate k clusters. Located units to pittance cluster is done with iteration format. The best suitable solution is determined with permutation approach using appointment of different clusters in every iteration (3).

Discriminant analysis, which purposes to estimate relations between categorical dependent variables and metric independent variables, is one of the multivariate statistical techniques (3). In this study, separation analysis is used for estimating the membership of group, determining variables which is efficient or not for group separation and testing honesty of clustering analysis results.

2. Data Sources and The Methodology

In our analysis, it is aimed to compare of indicators Global Summary Innovation Index (GSII), information and communications technology expenditures of World countries. It is used World Bank indicators and applied the Hierarchical Clustering Method, Discriminant Analysis and Correlation Analysis.

2.1. Selection of Innovation Indicators

The European Innovation Scoreboard uses data for 39 countries indicators divided over 5 broad innovation dimensions (Table 1). It is used data which Global innovation performance is measured by a composite index, the *Global Summary Innovation Index* (GSII) in this study.

Table 1: Global Innovation Scoreboard (GIS) indicators and sources	
1 INNOVATION DRIVERS	
1.1 New S&E graduates (S&E graduates as a promille of the population between 20 and 29 years)	UNESCO
1.2 Labour force with completed tertiary education ((The percentage of the working age population (between 25 and 64 years) with a tertiary education))	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
1.3 Researchers per million population (involved in creative innovative activities)	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
2 KNOWLEDGE CREATION	
2.1 Public R&D expenditures (minus business sector expenditures on R&D. For some countries data have been estimated)	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators), World Development Indicators, own estimates
2.2 Business R&D expenditures (For some countries data have been estimated)	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators), World Development Indicators, own estimates
2.3 Scientific articles per million population	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
3 DIFFUSION	
3.1 ICT expenditures (Data were taken from WITSA/IDC's Digital Planet report)	WITSA/IDC (Digital Planet 2004)
4 APPLICATIONS	
4.1 Exports of high-tech products	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
4.2 Share of medium-high/high-tech activities in manufacturing value added (Employment in medium-high and high-tech manufacturing as a percent of total employment)	UNIDO (Industrial Development Scoreboard)
5 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY	
5.1 EPO patents per million population ((EPO patents are here defined as the number of patent applications at the European Patent Office (EPO))	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators)
5.2 USPTO patents per million population (USPTO patents are here defined as the number of granted patents by the US Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO))	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators)
5.3 Triad patents per million population (A patent is a triad patent if and only if it is filed at the European Patent Office and the Japanese Patent Office (JPO) and granted by the US Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO))	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators)

Source : 2006 “Global Innovation Scoreboard” (GIS) Report

It is given GIS data availability (Table 2).

Combining data from Eurostat, World Bank (World Development Indicators), OECD, UNESCO, UNIDO and WITSA/IDC, it was possible to include 12 indicators in the GIS. The indicators and their data sources are given in Table 2. For most of the five EIS innovation dimensions (identified in bold in Table 2), there are data for at least 2 indicators, with the exception of only one indicator for the diffusion category.

Table 2: GIS indicators and sources	
1 INNOVATION DRIVERS	
1.1 New S&E graduates	UNESCO
1.2 Labour force with completed tertiary education	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
1.3 Researchers per million population	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
2 KNOWLEDGE CREATION	
2.1 Public R&D expenditures	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators), World Development Indicators, own estimates
2.2 Business R&D expenditures	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators), World Development Indicators, own estimates
2.3 Scientific articles per million population	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
3 DIFFUSION	
3.1 ICT expenditures	WITSA/IDC (Digital Planet 2004)
4 APPLICATIONS	
4.1 Exports of high-tech products	World Bank (World Development Indicators)
4.2 Share of medium-high/high-tech activities in manufacturing value added	UNIDO (Industrial Development Scoreboard)
5 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY	
5.1 EPO patents per million population	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators)
5.2 USPTO patents per million population	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators)
5.3 Triad patents per million population	OECD (Main Science and Technology Indicators)

Source : 2006 “Global Innovation Scoreboard” (GIS) Report

Table 3: GIS data availability

	REFERENCE YEAR													BASE YEAR												
	%	1.1	1.2	1.3	2.1	2.2	2.3	3.1	4.1	4.2	5.1	5.2	5.3	%	1.1	1.2	1.3	2.1	2.2	2.3	3.1	4.1	4.2	5.1	5.2	5.3
	97	90	84	100	100	100	98	96	100	100	100	100	100	90	84	53	100	86	86	88	86	100	100	100	100	100
Argentina	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	83	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Brazil	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	67	X	--	X	--	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Australia	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
New Zealand	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
South Africa	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	67	X	--	X	--	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Canada	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Mexico	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	75	X	--	X	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
United States	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
China	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Hong Kong	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
India	83	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	67	--	--	X	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Japan	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Korea, Rep.	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Singapore	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
European Union	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Austria	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	83	X	--	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Belgium	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Cyprus	92	X	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X
Czech Republic	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Denmark	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Estonia	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	83	X	--	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Finland	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
France	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Germany	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Greece	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	83	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Hungary	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Ireland	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Italy	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Latvia	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Lithuania	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Luxembourg	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	75	--	--	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Malta	83	X	--	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	67	X	--	X	--	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Netherlands	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Poland	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Portugal	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Slovak Republic	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Slovenia	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Spain	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Sweden	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
United Kingdom	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Bulgaria	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Croatia	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	67	X	--	X	--	--	X	--	X	X	X	X	X
Romania	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Russian Fed.	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Turkey	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Iceland	92	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X
Norway	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Switzerland	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	75	X	--	X	--	--	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Israel	100	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	92	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	X	X

1.1: New S&E graduates; 1.2: Labour force with completed tertiary education; 1.3: Researchers per million population; 2.1: Public R&D expenditures; 2.2: Business R&D expenditures; 2.3: Scientific articles per million population; 3.1: ICT expenditures as a share of GDP; 4.1: Exports of high-tech products out of all exports; 4.2: Share of medium-high/high-tech activities in manufacturing value added; 5.1: EPO patents per million population; 5.2: USPTO patents per million population; 5.3: Triad patents per million population

Source : 2006 “Global Innovation Scoreboard” (GIS) Report

2.2. Global Summary Innovation Index (GSII)

2.2.1. GSII – reference year

Global innovation performance is measured by a composite index, the *Global Summary Innovation Index* (GSII). This composite index is calculated as follows for the both the base year and the reference year, i.e. the year for which most recent data are available:

Step 1: Re-scale the reference and base year data for each indicator using the following formula:

$$X'_c = \frac{\sqrt{X_c} - \sqrt{MIN("X_i)}}{\sqrt{MAX("X_i)} - \sqrt{MIN("X_i)}}$$

A square root transformation is used to reduce the impact of both outliers and of skewed data distributions. The numerator takes the difference between the square root of the data value for country *c* and the square root of the lowest or minimum value found for that indicator for all countries. The denominator takes the difference between the square root of the largest or maximum value found for that indicator for all countries and the lowest or minimum value found for that indicator for all countries.

Step 2: Calculate the Global Summary Innovation Index as the average of the re-scaled indicator values, using equal weights for all indicators except for the business R&D indicator, which receives a weight twice that of the other indicators.

Step 3: Calculate sub composite indicators for each of the 5 innovation dimensions, by first taking the sum of the re-scaled indicator values in each of the dimensions and then divide by the total number of indicators for which data are available for that country (1) .

2.2.2. GSII – growth rate

The rate of change between the reference and base year composite indicator scores is defined as the growth rate of the GSII. Table 4 summarizes information regarding data used for the reference and base years. For calculating the reference and base GSII scores for determining the GSII growth rate.

- For the base year the same methodology is followed as that explained in section 2.2.1 to calculate the *GSII_Base*;
- For the reference year, the same methodology is used *but* only those reference year data for which base year data are also available are used to calculate the *GSII_Reference* (1).

Table 4: GIS indicators-reference and base years		
	Reference Years*	Base Year**
1.1 New S&E graduates	2004	Average for [2000-2002]
1.2 Labour force with completed tertiary education	2001	Average for [1997-1999]
1.3 Researchers per million population	2002	Average for [1997-1999]
2.1 Public R&D expenditures	2003	Average for [1999-2001]
2.2 Business R&D expenditures	2003	Average for [1999-2001]
2.3 Scientific articles per million population	2001	Average for [1997-1999]
3.1 ICT expenditures	2004	Average for [2000-2002]
4.1 Exports of high-tech products	2003	Average for [1999-2001]
4.2 Share of medium-high/high-tech activities in manufacturing value added	2000	1990
5.1 EPO patents per million population***	Average for [2000-2002]	Average for [1996-1998], [1997-1999] and [1998-2000]
5.2 USPTO patents per million population***	Average for [2000-2002]	Average for [1996-1998], [1997-1999] and [1998-2000]
5.3 Triad patents per million population***	Average for [2000-2002]	Average for [1996-1998], [1997-1999] and [1998-2000]

* Or most recent year. ** Or comparable lagged average. *** For the patent indicators 3 year averages have been used to reduce the impact of sometimes large year-to-year fluctuations ('volatility').

Source : 2006 “Global Innovation Scoreboard” (GIS) Report

The GSII growth rate, $GSII_Trend$, is then calculated as:

$$GSII_Trend = 100 * \sqrt{\frac{GSII_Reference}{GSII_Base}} - 100$$

The square root reflects the one-year gap between the reference and base year. GSII scores are given for all countries in “GSII scores and country codes” (1). It is taken to compare countries data that have information and communications technology expenditures.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Hierarchical Clustering Analysis

There are lots of approach to determine cluster number in the application of *K*-Means Clustering Method (3). We have chosen “to decide thereby investigation of dendrograms which are obtained from hierarchical clustering techniques” which is one of these approaches. Hierarchical clustering analysis was done related to GISS, “Squared Euclid Distance” and “Ward Method” were used. The countries take shape in seven groups in respect of cluster number result which are formed by hierarchical method result and Turkey is the same clustering with Argentina, Brazil, Czech Republic and South Africa according to GISS index of Turkey (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dendrogram using Average Linkage (Between Groups)

According to dendrogram, it is determined that there are 7 clusters with regard to GSII, % of GDP and per capita of technologic expenditures.

3.2. K-Means Clustering Analysis

K-Means Clustering Analysis result is given in the following Table 5.

Table 5. Clustering Member

Cluster	Case Number
First Cluster	BGR, ESP, GRC, ITA, MEX, POL, PRT, ROM, RUS
Second Cluster	CHE, FIN, GBR, JPN, SGP, SWE, USA
Third Cluster	AUS, AUT, BEL, CAN, DEU, DNK, FRA, IRL, NLD, NOR
Fourth Cluster	CHN, HUN, IND, SVK
Fifth Cluster	ISR, KOR
Sixth Cluster	HKG, NZL
Seventh Cluster	ARG, BRA, CZE, TUR, ZAF

Table 6. Clustering Analysis ANOVA Results

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
Zscore(GSII)	5,862	6	,088	32	66,361	,000
Zscore(TECGDP)	5,132	6	,225	32	22,783	,000
Zscore(TECPERCA)	5,669	6	,125	32	45,474	,000

It is seen that the index is significant in $N=39$ country clustering ($P<0.05$).

Table 7. Centers for $K=7$

Centers							
GSII	-0.91812835	1.32737507	1.32737507	-0.93114037	0.98162702	-0.03331078	-1.01181492
TECGDP	-1.2981932	0.8714267	-0.2677549	-0.3421006	0.7455503	1.7092916	0.9438056
TECPERCA	-0.8888411	1.2681732	0.7030952	-1.0966073	-0.2149511	0.8058436	-0.9407901

Clustering Analysis is a method which is intended for obtaining hypothetic results. Hence, the data should be analyzed to discuss the most suitable method as a result of data study (3). Obtained results by separation analysis are examined the following.

3.3. Discriminant Analysis

Some assumptions are provided for separation analysis being optimal and reducing incorrect classification. The most important assumptions of separation analysis are equal (homogenous) covariance, multicollinearity and Normality. Box' s M test was used for testing assumption of equal covariance. It can be seen that the null hypothesis is in form of "The groups' covariance matrixs are equal" in Table 8. Besides, in Table 8, we can see that the null hypothesis can not be rejected at (0.05) significant level, then groups are equal according to covariance matrixs. The result of applied separation analysis was achieved.

Table 8. Box's *M* Test

Tests for Homogeneity of Covariances:			
	Statistic	df	Pr
Box.M	44.81274	36	0.1488470

Table 9. Wilks' Lambda (*U*) Statistics

Tests for the Equality of Means (Group Variable: cluster.id) :					
	Statistics	F	df1	df2	Pr
Wilks Lambda	0.007	23.366	18	85.338	0.0000e+000
* Tests assume covariance homoscedasticity.					

Table 10. Plug-in Classification Results

Plug-in classification table:									
	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	Error	Posterior.Error
G1	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0261346
G2	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0691047
G3	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0.0116765
G4	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0.0930412
G5	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.0042024
G6	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0.0001385
G7	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0.0786829
Overall								0	0.0412813
(from=rows,to=columns) Rule Mean Square Error: 0.01515082 (conditioned on the training data)									

Table 11. Cross-validation table

Cross-validation table:									
	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	Error	Posterior.Error
G1	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.0380016
G2	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0.1428571	0.2089111
G3	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0.0000000	-0.0423308
G4	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0.0000000	-0.0601387
G5	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0.0000000	0.0475717
G6	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0.0000000	0.0005013
G7	0	0	0	1	0	0	4	0.2000000	0.2322000
Overall								0.0512821	0.0614789
(from=rows,to=columns)									

94.87179% of original grouped cases correctly classified.

Figure 2. Binary Comparison of GSII, TECGDP and TECPERCA

3.4. Correlation Analysis

This article compares with “Global Summary Innovation Scoreboard” (GSII) with information and communications technology expenditures (% of GDP, per capita) some of World countries compares.

H_0 : There is no relation between variables.

H_1 : There is relation between variables.

Table 12. Correlation Analysis Result

	Zscore(GSII)	Zscore(TECGDP)	Zscore(TECPERCA)
Zscore(GSII)	1,000	0.4144508	0.8702085
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.0087	0.000
Zscore(TECGDP)	0.4144508	1,000	0.4296516
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.0087		0.0063
Zscore(TECPERCA)	0.8702085	0.4296516	1,000
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.0063	

* Pearson's product-moment correlation, significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

KAYNAKLAR

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